

Toward a possible integration of NeuronGPU in NEST

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NeuronGPU is a library for MPI-GPU simulation of large scale networks of spiking neurons, written in the CUDA/C++ programming languages. Currently, this library includes different adaptive-exponential-integrate-and-fire (AdEx) multisynapse models, with current or conductance based synapses, together with user definable models, and several devices, as Poisson signal generators, spike generators, multimeters, spike recorders. Several connection rules are available. In addition to the standard synapses, the library includes STDP synapses. The numerical solution of the differential equations that describe the neuronal dynamics is based on a GPU implementation of the 5th order Runge-Kutta method with adaptive step-size control. On a single Nvidia GeForce RTX 2080 Ti GPU board it is possible to simulate the activity of 1 million multisynapse conductance-based AdEx neurons with 1000 synapse per neurons, for a total of 1 billion synapse, in about 71 seconds for each second of neural activity, with about 97 seconds of build time.

Recently, having in mind the possibility of integrating this library into the well-known NEST simulator [1], NeuronGPU has been equipped with a Python interface, analogous to the one of the NEST simulator. The next step of this integration, which is currently in progress, is the implementation of an interface, either based on the MUSIC interface [2], or on more specialized functions, to manage a quick exchange of information between NEST and NeuronGPU in both directions. With this interface, the NEST capabilities will be further extended to include the possibility of simulation on GPU supports. Furthermore, this interface would allow the unique possibility to simulate hybrid networks, with a very large number of neurons and connections based on simpler models simulated on the GPU side, and a smaller number of neurons and connections based on more complex and detailed models simulated on the CPU side and used both for consistency checks and to shed light on the relationship between the dynamics of the network and that of the neuron internal variables.

Acknowledgements

This work has been supported by the European Union Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation program under the FET Flagship Human Brain Project (grant agreement SGA3 n. 945539 and grant agreement SGA2 n. 785907) and by the INFN APE Parallel/Distributed Computing laboratory. The implementation of the AdEx model of this library closely follows the `aeif_cond_beta_multisynapse` model present in the NEST simulator and implemented by one of the authors, B. Golosio, in collaboration with Prof. Hans Ekkehard Plesser and Dr. Tanguy Fardet.

References

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